

Charging Ahead: Assessing China's Leverage and the EU's Strategic Dilemma in the EV Transition

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Abstract

This article explores China's growing geoeconomic leverage in the global electric vehicle (EV) and battery supply chain, examining its implications for the European Union's industrial strategic autonomy while advancing its ambitious green transition. Applying the framework of Blackwill & Harris (2016), it analyzes three core drivers of China's leverage: centrality in global supply chains, monopoly over key technologies and raw materials, and monopsony power as a dominant buyer and processor. China's dominance is underpinned by its control of critical minerals, vast manufacturing capacity, and technological innovation, particularly in lithium-iron-phosphate (LFP) battery technology. This paper then examines the EU's response through tariffs, industrial policies, and diversification efforts under its "de-risking" strategy. However, this paper argues that these measures are insufficient to resolve Europe's structural dependencies on Chinese imports. Challenges such as slow domestic capacity development, higher production costs, fragmented political consensus, and regulatory constraints hinder the EU's ability to reshape the status quo. The article concludes that while China's leverage can act as both a tool of cooperation and coercion, the EU must urgently scale domestic production, incentivize critical raw material investments, and strengthen regulatory coherence to safeguard industrial competitiveness and climate goals. Without deeper structural reforms and greater strategic unity, the EU remains vulnerable to external pressures in the rapidly evolving green economy.

Keywords: EU-China relations, green transition, electric vehicles (EVs), battery supply chain, critical raw materials, strategic autonomy, geoeconomic leverage

Introduction

The race to dominate green transition has transformed clean energy technologies and critical resources into powerful tools of geopolitical leverage, reshaping alliances and sparking new rivalries in the global quest for sustainable supremacy. For instance, in August 2022, the U.S. introduced the Inflation Reduction Act (IRA), aiming to invest \$369 billion in clean energy initiatives. The act focuses on boosting domestic production of key technologies like electric vehicles and renewable energy components, with the dual goals of reducing emissions and reestablishing the U.S. as a global leader in green technology manufacturing (Zabelin & von Dongen, 2024). The European Union has similarly introduced the Green Deal Industrial Plan, which seeks to maintain competitiveness and reduce dependency on key imports while accelerating the transition to a net-zero economy (Temple-West, 2024). Key pillars of the Plan include the Critical Raw Materials Act and the Net-Zero Industry Act, both passed in 2024, which aim to secure resources, boost domestic clean technology manufacturing, and address global competition for critical materials essential for decarbonization efforts (Canestrini, 2024). In Asia, China is spearheading clean energy technology by producing over 80% of the world's solar panels, leveraging its dominance in those supply chains to "entrench its global leadership" (International Energy Agency, 2022; Zabelin & von Dongen, 2024, para. 2). Indeed, this global shift towards green infrastructure reflects the growing recognition that energy security, technological innovation, and climate action are deeply interconnected (Zabelin and von Dongen,

2024). This quest for geopolitical leverage amid the green transition is especially pronounced amid international efforts to decrease dependence on fossil fuels by investing in batteries to power the new age of electric vehicles.

As Leslie Gelb—a longtime foreign policy expert, and former New York Times commentator—expressed, “Beijing has been playing the new economic game at a maestro level” (Walt, 2010, para. 9). Indeed, China has emerged as a global leader in electric vehicles (EVs) and battery manufacturing, producing 62% of global EVs in 2022 and accounting for 77% of global battery manufacturing capacity. Dominated by giants like CATL and FDB, Chinese manufacturers now produce 75% of the world’s lithium-ion batteries, underscoring their pivotal role in the EV supply chain (Ezell, 2024). Furthermore, with batteries accounting for 40% of the costs to produce EVs, China aims to solidify its dominance over critical raw materials (Vox, 2024).

In response to China's role as a globally significant supplier and manufacturer in EV production and its potential geopolitical leverage, the EU has implemented measures to protect its automotive industry and reduce dependence on Chinese imports. In October 2024, the EU imposed additional tariffs on Chinese EVs, with rates reaching up to 45.3% for certain manufacturers (Blenkinsop, 2024). This decision followed an investigation that concluded Chinese EV producers benefited from substantial state subsidies, enabling them to offer vehicles at lower prices and posing a threat to European manufacturers and European competitiveness (Blenkinsop, 2025).

While the EU's pursuit of strategic autonomy and its de-risking strategy, as outlined by von der Leyen, highlight the bloc's urgent need to diversify energy imports and reduce dependencies, Russia's invasion of Ukraine served as a critical tipping point (Center for

European Policy Studies, 2023). The crisis exposed Europe's over-reliance on external suppliers, particularly for energy, reinforcing the imperative to secure more resilient and diversified supply chains in key sectors, including renewable energy and battery production. However, despite numerous reports and academic articles documenting China's dominant role in the energy transition and battery production, a gap exists in understanding how China's market position translates into geopolitical power (Chan, 2025; Zhang and Chen, 2022). Further research, through analytical explorations of case studies, is needed to analyze how China's control over critical mineral supply chains and its strategic investments in renewable technologies enhance its geopolitical influence, and how this leverage impacts global energy security and bilateral relations with the EU (Downie, 2022). Thus, this article aims to investigate the following research question: How does China's dominance in the EV and battery supply chain translate into geo-economic leverage, thereby reshaping EU-China relations and de-risking strategies?

This study fills a critical research gap and presents a novel application of Blackwill & Harris' (2016) framework to analyze China's geo-economic leverage. This paper argues that China's dominance in the EV and battery supply chain grants it significant geo-economic leverage, driven by its centrality in global value chains, monopoly over key technologies and materials, and monopsony power as the world's largest buyer and processor of critical minerals. While the EU has introduced defensive measures like tariffs to reduce dependency, these responses fail to address the structural vulnerabilities in Europe's green technology sector, leaving it exposed to China's leverage, which can function both as a tool of cooperation and coercion in shaping the future of EU-China relations.

This research will explain Blackwill & Harris' (2016) theoretical framework before analyzing the three factors contributing to China's position and ability to achieve geo-economic leverage. The

analysis then illustrates how this geoeconomic leverage has geopolitical implications, especially in the context of EU-China relations, as the EU is navigating the dual challenge of strategic autonomy or strategic dependence. The critical discussion attempts to elucidate the limitations constraining the EU's leverage and ability to alter the status quo. The analysis then moves to a review of key policy recommendations, followed by concluding reflections and suggestions for future research directions.

1. Theoretical Framework

Geoeconomic endowments refer to the inherent resources, capabilities, and structural advantages that a nation possesses, which can be strategically utilized to achieve geopolitical and economic objectives (Blackwill & Harris, 2016). Certain structural features, or geoeconomic endowments, determine how effectively a country can wield geoeconomic tools. While geopolitical power is well-studied, geoeconomics lacks a comprehensive framework, leaving ambiguity about the tools available and the factors that enable states to use them successfully (Blackwill & Harris, 2016).

Blackwill & Harris (2016) argue that effective geoeconomic leverage depends on economic endowments. Their book proposes four different endowments: control over outbound investments, domestic market features, influence over commodity and energy flows, and centrality to the global financial system. This analysis will exclusively focus on the influence over commodity and energy flows to assess China's ability to achieve geoeconomic leverage on the global battery and EV markets (Blackwill & Harris, 2016). According to Blackwill & Harris (2016), three specific variables constitute this endowment and can determine how successfully a country can leverage its geoeconomic standing. First, centrality as an endowment involves a country's role as a key transit hub or

manufacturing centre. Second, monopoly power refers to a state's market ownership and lastly, monopsony power refers to the influence that is derived from being the world's leading customer. This article will explore the centrality of China as a transit point and a hub of strategic investments in efforts to reduce fossil fuel dependence. China's monopoly power will be analyzed in terms of the dominance of the supply chain and market influence through technological innovation. Lastly, China's monopsony power is under-explored, which is why this article aims to shed light on how China's domestic demand and purchasing power contribute to the consolidation of geoeconomic leverage. In the next section, this essay will conduct an in-depth analysis of the three variables underpinning China's geoeconomic endowment to evaluate its capacity to influence commodity and energy flows.

2. Analysis

2.1 Centrality

First, Blackwill & Harris' (2016) variable of centrality, refers to a nation's importance within a global economic system. This importance is determined by its role in connecting buyers, sellers, and markets, acting as a critical hub in supply chains. Recent scholarship in International Political Economy (IPE) has increasingly investigated the structural context of the international economic system in which states are embedded and faced with structural power asymmetries (Snidal et al., 2024). IPE scholars conceptualize the global economic system as a hierarchical network of interdependencies where states hold varying degrees of influence based on their position within these interconnected structures (Slaughter, 2018). This emerging body of literature, called "new structuralism," highlights the increasing concentration of power within global economic networks. It emphasizes how these networks have evolved into "hub-and-spoke" systems, where states that establish themselves as central hubs gain significant power (Farrell and Newman, 2023; Snidal et al., 2024). Controlling such central hubs allows the

beneficiary of this power to manipulate or even weaponize interdependence for strategic advantages, potentially turning economic ties into tools of influence or coercion. Since hubs provide significant benefits and are challenging to bypass, states that dominate them wield substantial leverage. At the same time, those excluded from these critical networks may face severe economic and geopolitical repercussions (Farrell & Newman, 2019).

When assessing the centrality of China as a transit point between major buyers and sellers in the battery and EV production, the reality is apparent that China's integration into the global value chains derives from dominating raw material processing, manufacturing, and export (Blackwill & Harris, 2016). China has become a central player in the global EV and battery industry by connecting upstream suppliers of raw materials with downstream global EV manufacturers. To understand this centrality, one must understand how China was able to position itself at the center of these markets. Indeed, as early as the 2000s, Chinese companies realized that they would struggle to achieve global competitiveness in internal combustion engine technologies (Yang, 2023). As a result, policymakers shifted their focus toward developing a globally competitive domestic industry in EVs to reduce reliance on foreign automotive technologies and dependence on oil imports (Ezell, 2024). China's reliance on crude oil imports, which amounted to 11.29 million bpd (barrels per day), made it the most significant oil importer in the world (Russell, 2024). However, this dependence on oil imports renders the state vulnerable to external oil shocks, market disruptions, price volatility, and geopolitical tensions (Russell, 2025). For example, trade disputes leading to tariffs on energy imports can disrupt supply chains and increase costs, as seen in recent U.S.-China trade tensions (Donovan & Nikoladze, 2024). With EV competitiveness becoming a national priority, China sought to position itself as a frontrunner

in the clean energy transition and reduce fossil fuel dependence, while simultaneously addressing the escalating air pollution crisis in China's densely populated megacities (Ezell, 2024).

To secure its central position in EV and battery manufacturing, China requires a stable and long-term access to the critical raw materials essential for battery production. This strategic necessity led to extensive upstream investments aimed at securing control over the global supply of minerals vital to the green energy transition. The materials demanded for EV battery production are graphite, lithium, cobalt, copper, phosphorus, manganese, and nickel (International Renewable Energy Agency, 2024). The reality of controlling critical minerals for the green technological transition has prompted China to ramp up investments in both domestic and international mining sectors. In line with this strategy, Chinese investment in the metal and mining sector, particularly through the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI), surged to its highest level in a decade in 2023, reaching \$19.4 billion (138 billion RMB), representing a 160% increase from 2022 (International Energy Agency, 2024, see p. 63). Under the BRI, China has also been actively investing in the acquisition of overseas mines, especially in Africa (Cooper, 2024). Another example is Indonesia, which, while contributing 52% of global mined nickel production, Chinese companies control 40% of Indonesia's total mined nickel output in 2023 (International Energy Agency, 2024).

Consequently, China's dominance across the global supply chain is reinforced by its position as an indispensable hub for battery component extraction and subsequent extensive refining and processing capabilities. BBC (2024) documented at least 62 mining projects worldwide where Chinese companies hold investment stakes (see Figure 1). Furthermore, China currently dominates the global supply of key battery materials, producing 99% of battery-grade graphite, over 60% of lithium chemicals, 40% of refined copper, more than 80% of refined magnet

rare earths, and 70% of refined cobalt (Cooper, 2024; Minnis, 2024). Domestically, China has been expanding its lithium production, increasing its share of global lithium mining from 6% in 2016 to 17% in 2023. By the mid-2020s, it is projected to surpass Chile as the world's second-largest lithium producer (Cooper, 2024). With 2/3 of the global "EV lithium-ion battery production capacities located in China" (Wang, 2022, p. 1), it is effectively spearheading control of this critical sector, giving domestic companies a stable supply chain (Yang, 2023). Thus, China's centrality in the EV and battery supply chains, contributes to its geo-economic leverage.

Figure 1

China has business interests in mining around the world
 Location of lithium, cobalt, nickel and manganese projects with a Chinese stake

Note. From BBC (2024).

2.2 Monopoly Power

Building on the previous analysis of China's role as a critical hub in global supply chains, its geo-economic leverage through a central transit position is closely intertwined with monopoly power, which it achieves through market dominance. Blackwill & Harris (2016) determine that monopoly power, which refers to a state's market ownership, is a key factor towards ensuring geo-economic leverage.

First, given China's strategic investments and control over supply chains to maintain its centrality and resource security in the critical raw materials industry, it has also established dominance in exporting refined battery materials, further solidifying its geo-economic leverage. Indeed, natural and refined battery-grade graphite are already under strict export controls from China (International Energy Agency, 2024). In addition to these controls, in January 2025, China's Commerce Minister declared plans to impose further export restrictions on the technology required to produce battery components and critical mineral processing. These restrictions would help China "retain its 70% grip on the global processing of lithium into the material needed to make EV batteries" (Reuters, 2025a, para. 4).

Second, China's global dominance in the battery and EV industry (see figure 2) is predated by companies such as BYD, which was a major producer of batteries for electronics in the 90s before EV manufacturing was pushed as a national priority and manufacturing capabilities were heavily expanded. From 2009 to 2022, the government invested over 200 billion RMB (\$29 billion) into subsidies and tax breaks for EV industries to incentivize critical growth in this sector (Yang, 2023). While this number is more narrowly focused on direct financial investments, Kennedy (2024) estimates the total accumulative government support from 2009 to 2023 to amount to \$230.9 billion. This amount includes broader categories of government aid such as infrastructure investment, industrial policy

initiatives, subsidies, tax incentives, research and development grants, and direct investments. As Yang (2023) demonstrates, these government subsidies were not limited to domestic companies but were also aimed at benefiting rising foreign companies, such as one of the biggest EV companies globally, Tesla. Tesla's Shanghai Gigafactory is its most productive manufacturing facility, responsible for producing over half of all Tesla vehicles delivered in 2022 (Yang, 2023).

Additionally, to qualify for consumer subsidies, even companies like GM and Tesla, who wanted to share their cars on the Chinese market, were required to use Chinese-made batteries (Yang, 2023). This expansion and subsequent market dominance became a wake-up call for American and European industries when CATL came to control almost two-thirds of the global EV battery market and supplied major Western companies such as Tesla, BMW, and Volkswagen (Hawkins, 2024a). In 2023, China accounted for 60% of worldwide EV sales, and in 2024, BYD surpassed Tesla in EV production, making it the new leading EV manufacturer worldwide (Ezell, 2024; Richter, 2025) (see figure 3). Indeed, in 2024, China's passenger car exports surged by nearly 20%, reaching almost five million vehicles (Euronews, 2025; Reuters, 2025b). Summarizing this argument, the accrued benefits of dominating the EV industry are two-fold. China can reduce dependence on Western-manufactured cars and simultaneously create lucrative export opportunities to sustain its economy.

Third, while critiques of China's increasing monopoly power in the EV industry often focus on political tensions, unfair trade practices, and government subsidies, this narrow perspective overlooks a fundamental reality: China's success is also driven by innovation and technological advancements, which have played a crucial role in its global competitiveness.

Figure 2

Note. From Swieboda (2025).

Figure 3

Note. The figure highlights EV sales by country and EVs as a share of all car sales. From Ezell, (2024).

As Kennedy (2024) reports, China argues that its global competitiveness and growing exports are the results of its own comparative advantage and high-quality products. Notably, China has been leading innovation in battery technology by eliminating the most expensive components, namely nickel, and cobalt, by replacing them with lithium-iron-phosphate (LFP). For much of the 21st century, LFP batteries were considered outdated and inferior to nickel manganese cobalt (NMC) batteries in energy density. From 2016 to 2018, LFP batteries only made up 10% of the global EV battery market, but today, their share has surged to 40% (Ezell, 2024). This shift was primarily driven by Chinese companies, particularly CATL (EV battery maker), which advanced LFP battery technology through research and innovation, challenging previous industry assumptions. In 2024, CATL unveiled

a new battery that could power a driving range of up to 1000 kilometers (621 miles) on a single charge (Reuters, 2024). Interestingly, LFP batteries are more environmentally friendly, safer, and cheaper, with previously critical components such as nickel and cobalt, no longer required (Reuters, 2024; Yang, 2023). Recent findings indicate that Chinese EV companies are approximately 30% faster in developing and launching new car models than traditional American, European, and Japanese automakers. This rapid innovation means Chinese brands rival and surpass other established names such as Tesla and BMW (Ezell, 2024).

China's economic partners contend that unfair trade practices and Chinese industrial strategy are to blame for current tensions. China defends itself by arguing that the high caliber of its businesses' output and the nation's inherent comparative advantage are the reasons behind its expanding exports. There is some truth to all perspectives, complicating the decision for appropriate responses. The reality is that Chinese EV companies have received extensive industrial policy support. Still, at the same time, their quality has improved, making them more and more appealing to both domestic and foreign consumers (Kennedy, 2024).

2.3 Monopsony Power

Monopsony power refers to the dominance of a buyer who faces little competition, allowing them to dictate terms to suppliers (Blackwill & Harris, 2016). This power is demonstrated on the market in multiple ways. First, China is leading the market in refining capabilities, refining almost three-quarters of the global supply of cobalt, despite not having any domestic production (Sall and Gross, 2025). A monopsony situation is subsequently created as mineral producers face one dominant client, namely Chinese refining facilities (Gulley, 2024). This poses a risk, as China's dominant position in critical material procurement could

enable it to exert pressure on suppliers or manipulate pricing to its advantage (Sall and Gross, 2025). Indeed, this monopsony power has already been visible as China increased restrictions on the export of these critical minerals nine times between 2009 and 2020 (Sall and Gross, 2025). In 2021, China released a negative list and banned foreign direct investments (FDI) in China's rare-earth mining projects (Global Times, 2021). These measures strengthen China's domestic control over rare-earth resources, safeguarding its supply while reinforcing its dominance in refining and processing capabilities. By restricting foreign investment, China ensures that global industries remain reliant on its rare-earth processing and exports, further solidifying its strategic position in the supply chain.

A second example is the Democratic Republic of Congo, which accounts for 70% of global cobalt production. However, Chinese companies own approximately 80% of the country's cobalt output, which is refined in China and then sold worldwide (Congressional-Executive Commission on China, 2023). Under a "resource-for-infrastructure" model (Baskaran, 2023, para. 5), China signed the Sino-Congolais des Mines (Sicomines) agreement in 2007, committing approximately \$3 billion in infrastructure investments in exchange for mining rights to deposits valued at \$93 billion. Linking this to monopsony power, China can dictate terms to suppliers as the DRC is left disadvantaged by limiting its ability to award extraction rights to the highest bidder. This not only restricts competition on price but also prevents the DRC from selecting investors that offer broader benefits, such as strong environmental, social, and governance (ESG) practices or commitments to developing local industries and infrastructure (Baskaran, 2023). Even on the Latin American continent, in Chile, China accounted for over 65% of Chile's mineral exports in 2021, totaling \$22.5 billion, representing approximately 6% of Chile's GDP (Hernandez-Roy et al., 2024).

Besides dominating refining capabilities, China's

market share in EV production has steadily increased and surpassed 76% in 2024 (Hawkins, 2024b). From January to October 2024, China accounted for 69% of global EV sales (Hawkins, 2024b). The surge in EV sales is, among other factors, driven by consistent advancements in the quality of Chinese EVs, particularly with innovations like LFP battery technology. These qualitative improvements have significantly boosted China's EV exports to high-income countries, with their share rising from 5% in 2018 to 60% in 2023 (Sall & Gross, 2025). This exponential growth can be explained by China shifting its policies to allow foreign automakers to produce their EVs in China without an “equal-share Chinese partner” (Sall & Gross, 2025, para. 20). Consequently, companies such as Tesla, BMW or Renault capitalized on these policy changes and established their production sites in China. As export shares increase, Western governments grow worried about being outcompeted by lower-priced EVs from China. However, Western tariffs on Chinese-made EVs and battery components cannot ignore the fact that a robust domestic demand has helped China stabilize and grow its industry. While the new energy vehicles (NEV) consumer subsidies have started to be phased out in 2022, the domestic demand has been successfully created (Hongpei, 2023). Indeed, in July 2024, over 50.8% of car sales were new energy vehicles (Bloomberg, 2024). According to a survey from AlixPartners (2021), over 50% of Chinese respondents expressed interest in purchasing EV cars, representing the highest proportion worldwide and two times the global average. This demand gives manufacturers a growing market that allows them to maintain high production volumes, achieve economies of scale, and remain competitive globally despite external trade barriers (Hawkins, 2024b). This section argues that China's monopsony power—rooted in its dominance as the world's leading buyer, refiner, and consumer of critical minerals—grants it significant geoeconomic leverage. By controlling demand and shaping supplier

terms, China is able to consolidate its influence across EV and battery supply chains.

3. Strategic Autonomy or Strategic Dependence? The EU's Response to China's Dominance of EV and Battery Supply Chain

The first part of this analysis demonstrated China's geoeconomic leverage in the global EV and battery industry. Understanding the three factors of centrality, monopsony, and monopoly power and their geopolitical implications is crucial in the subsequent analysis and contextualization of EU-China relations. With geopolitical leverage understood as a “function of the export state's leverage and the target state's vulnerability” (Downie, 2022, p. 2), China's strides to consolidate its dominance in EV and battery supply chains presents a critical urgency to assess the implications for the EU's strategic autonomy.

This next section will elaborate on some of the main challenges faced by the EU in achieving strategic autonomy in the EV and battery market before presenting recommendations for policies and future windows of opportunity. Understanding China's leverage not only helps explain Europe's vulnerabilities but also highlights the urgent need for a comprehensive response. This response needs to move beyond reactive measures like tariffs and instead address structural dependencies, foster innovation, and strengthen Europe's green technology sector.

In the context of EU-China relations, it is crucial to recognize the double-edged nature of China's leverage. Downie (2022) argues that geoeconomic leverage operates along a spectrum, ranging from coercion to strategic incentives. At one extreme, energy exports and supply chain control can be weaponized to exert economic pressure and impose costs on dependent states. On the other, leverage can function as a diplomatic tool, encouraging cooperation or offering economic advantages to influence strategic decisions. Importantly, the leverage of exporting states will depend on “excess

resources, a supportive institutional environment, and market dominance” (Downie, 2022, p. 1). Furthermore, the scope of geopolitical leverage that the exporting state can gain depends on the importing states’ vulnerabilities. These vulnerabilities are, in turn, shaped by the latter’s level of exposure and ability to withstand market disruptions or external shocks.

The EU is the single largest market for China’s EV exports by value, as China’s global EV exports have surged since 2021 to reach over \$44 billion in 2024 (Webster, 2025). From 2020 to 2023, EV exports increased by 851%, while the largest share of these exports (40%) went to Europe (Ezell, 2024). Concerning batteries, China accounts for half of all EU battery imports, equaling €11bn worth of EV batteries (Spisak, 2024). Furthermore, China supplies 100% of the EU’s heavy rare earth elements (European Commission, 2023). The main challenge facing the EU in light of China’s growing geoeconomic leverage is to prevent a scenario where meeting EV targets comes at the cost of industrial decline or geopolitical weakness.

3.1 Limitations of EU Leverage that Constrain its Abilities to Alter the Status-quo

First, while intended industrial policies can boost domestic production, operationalizing these industries is not an instant result. In 2018, the Commission designated battery self-sufficiency as a strategic imperative for the EU’s clean energy transition. By 2021, total investments in the battery value chain had reached €127 billion. Looking ahead, an estimated €382 billion in further funding is anticipated by 2030 to establish a fully self-sufficient battery industry (European Commission, 2022). However, while battery production is set to increase, the looming shortage of raw materials and building infrastructure capacities is set to delay self-sufficiency until 2030 (European Court of

Auditors, 2023). Additionally, despite significant investments in battery production, the Swedish battery manufacturer Northvolt recently declared bankruptcy (Do Prado et al., 2025). These challenges ranging from innovation bottlenecks to high costs and startup failures, contribute to the EU’s continued vulnerability and dependence on Chinese-imported batteries to meet the surging EV demand.

Second, Europe’s higher energy and labor costs and stricter environmental rules can make European-made batteries pricier. This reality will test the limits of subsidy support and the willingness of consumers to pay more. These findings become even more critical, as by 2023, China’s “battery cell production was more than double its domestic demand” (International Energy Agency, 2024, p. 31) and companies provided price advantages based on mass production and economy of scale (Wang, 2022). This means that as manufacturing capabilities exceed domestic demand, they will lead to increased export pushes. China’s excess production could push global battery prices down, which in turn will complicate Western producers’ ability to compete and increase their reliance on Chinese imports (International Energy Agency, 2024). These geoeconomic leverages have geopolitical implications, as they risk undermining the EU’s de-risk strategies of diversifying its supply chains and seeking alternative sources of critical minerals.

Third, trade measures such as tariffs present a double-edged sword. On the one hand, they can promote more fair competition, protect domestic industries, shield them from being undercut by cheaper imports, and encourage local investments to enhance job creation and technological advancements (McHugh & Moritsugu, 2024). On the other hand, tariffs are not considered to be the proper response to strengthening EU competitiveness. Interestingly, the anti-subsidy probes were not launched from industry complaints but from the Commission’s own investigation into what it considers to be Chinese industrial dominance undermining EU

competitiveness. In response to investigations, the EU has imposed tariffs of 38% on Chinese EVs, while the U.S. has imposed tariffs exceeding 100% (Ezell, 2024). However, the imposition of tariffs overlooks the reality of China's leverage and risks provoking retaliatory tariffs. As the combined EV market share of Volkswagen, BMW, Audi, Mercedes, and Porsche in China is about 5%, China can still exert considerable pressure (Tyborski & Fasse, 2025). Leading up to the EU's decision to impose tariffs on Chinese EVs in 2024, Chinese officials lobbied Member States against these tariffs, with reports, although unofficial, emerging that Chinese authorities were informally requesting automakers to pause investments in EU countries that supported the tariffs (Featherston, 2024). With production in China, EU car makers will likely transfer the increased costs onto European consumers (Spisak, 2024). Only the EU would profit from such tariffs by cashing in 2.3 to 3 billion euros in tariff revenue (Spisak, 2024).

The vote on increasing tariffs from 10% to 35% on Chinese EVs passed narrowly in October 2024, as many Member States abstained (see figure 4) (Spisak, 2024). These retaliatory actions have the power to divide the EU members, who, amid the unease of provoking a trade war, only 10 out of the 27 governments firmly voted in favor of the EV tariff decision (Featherston, 2024). Germany requested lower tariffs in fear of Chinese retaliatory actions against the German auto industry, while France's President Macron argued that "We don't protect enough" (Chen and Rose, 2024, para. 3; Verhelst and Zimmermann, 2024). Another example is how each member state has the final say on investment screenings, which renders the patchwork that is the EU position more difficult to navigate and construct collective leverage. This shows how, amid fear of economic fallout, the EU is unable to ensure unity, which further challenges the management of EU-China relations in pursuing

Figure 4

Note. From Featherston (2024).

a unified and strong strategic autonomy. Fourth, the EU prides itself on operating within a rules-based trade system, meaning its tools must be WTO-compliant and evidence-based. Naturally, it is operating with more constraints and cannot, for example, copy the U.S.'s Inflation Reduction Act (IRA), as such discriminatory incentives of providing tax credits to encourage the consumption of domestic products would violate EU internal market rules and likely WTO rules. Furthermore, the EU is already facing retaliatory actions by China, in response to the EV tariffs. China launched its own trade probes, conducting anti-dumping and anti-subsidy investigations into EU exports of pork and dairy (Ledman et al., 2024). Thus, while upholding global norms, the legal caution can be seen as limiting Europe's geo-economic leverage vis-à-vis a state-capitalist China.

Lastly, the biggest challenge facing the EU is not only how to manage economic and political trade-offs but also the trade-off between Europe's consumer and climate goals. This trilemma of balancing the green transition, affordability for consumers, and economic sovereignty, will test EU decision-makers on whether to hit climate targets despite relating to Chinese imports or to

prioritize the protection of industries and resilience, which is accompanied by high costs or slower EV rollouts. The European Court of Auditors' (2023) report notes that although the strategic action plan outlines relevant goals, it lacks quantified, time-bound targets, particularly regarding EU battery production. This omission makes it harder to assess whether Europe can meet its 2035 zero-emission targets with domestic capacity or whether it will remain reliant on imports, jeopardizing supply security and the competitiveness of the European battery value chain. This inherent tension limits how far the EU can push on any lever without undermining another goal. Politically, leaders must answer to voters on both the cost of living, jobs, and security, making the path fraught. Already, Chinese car manufacturers such as BYD and Geely and battery manufacturer CATL have invested in EV facilities across Spain, Slovakia, Germany, and Hungary (CATL, 2024; Piovaccari, 2025; Reuters, 2024). Some EU policymakers consider such strategies of solidifying a European presence through joint ventures to benefit the European market by localizing production and providing manufacturing jobs. However, these ventures also raise questions about technological dependence. They could face fierce barriers through the EU's foreign subsidies regulation, which allows the blocking of companies from operating in the EU if they are deemed to profit from foreign governmental subsidies (European Commission, n.d.; Spisak, 2024). The delicate balance between permitting Chinese state-subsidized companies to develop facilities on European soil and opposing their integration into the European EV supply chain remains unresolved. The ensuing political debate centers on the trade-off between safeguarding European competitiveness in this strategic industry by bolstering domestic production and enabling European consumers to benefit from more affordable Chinese-made EVs to accelerate the green transition (Spisak, 2024).

4. Policy Recommendations

First, the EU should scale up domestic production, which the European Commission and the European Investment Bank (EIB) hope to boost by launching a new partnership to strengthen the EU's battery manufacturing industry, which includes a €200 million top-up to the InvestEU program via the Innovation Fund. These commitments aim to help fund innovative battery projects and bridge the gap between research and development and commercial deployment. Additionally, the Innovation Fund currently offers €1 billion in grants to support EV battery cell manufacturing. At the same time, the EIB plans to invest another €1.8 billion across the battery value chain, from raw materials to recycling (European Commission, 2024). Furthermore, the EU's new Industrial Action Plan for the automotive sector (2025) rightly prioritizes batteries in its "Battery Booster" package. However, many of its pledges still need to materialize in actual funding and projects on the ground. Accelerating the disbursement of funds, simplifying grant procedures, and mobilizing private capital via public-private partnerships are considered urgent steps (European Commission, 2025).

In addition, Webster's (2025) analysis proposed that Germany should step up with the other Member States, playing a critical supporting role, as it "has the fiscal space for transformational investments" (para. 8). Indeed, Germany's government debt-to-gross domestic product (GDP) stands at 63% compared to other countries like France with 111% (Webster, 2025). Furthermore, the European Commissioner for Trade, Valdis Dombrovskis, argues that one of the primary causes of Germany's ongoing underinvestment is the debt brake (Sorgi, 2024). Among the G7, Germany's economy was the only one that shrank in 2023, which warrants the need for reforms of the debt brake to encourage investments in infrastructure and defense (Webster, 2025). Nonetheless, as Connolly (2025) reported in

March 2025, newly elected Chancellor Merz was able to secure the Green party's support to push ahead with his proposal to relax the debt brake. Investing in domestic electric vehicle production is also a strategic move for Germany and other European countries. By decreasing dependence on Chinese EVs, Europe can address a potential security vulnerability while safeguarding jobs in a sector that supports 6.1% of the EU's total employment directly and indirectly (Webster, 2025).

Second, a key vulnerability for Europe is its dependence on imported critical raw materials (CRMs), such as lithium, cobalt, nickel, and rare earths, which are essential for batteries and EV motors. To counter this dependence, the EU has initiated a new strategy, which aims to sign strategic partnerships with resource-rich countries. However, as Tenev (2024) warns, these partnerships will only fulfill their intended purpose of de-risking, if the European industries invest in CRM supply chains in those partner countries. As for now, "the incentives for European companies to enter mining and processing operations in these markets are too weak" (Tenev, 2024, para. 3). One example is Namibia, where EU partnership has not produced significant results, and "may even be benefitting Chinese firms at European expense" (Tenev, 2024, para. 4). Indeed, the laws in Namibia require local processing of CRMs, which adds costs and complexity. Consequently, EU firms face increased operational costs in the short term, as they are required to comply with international environmental, social, and governance (ESG) standards. Chinese companies do not face such constraints and can absorb costs, thus enjoying greater freedom in negotiating minerals-for-infrastructure deals under the Belt and Road initiative (Tenev, 2024). Instead of de-risking from China, EU efforts may entrench China's dominance by improving the investment environment without ensuring that EU firms can participate. In its attempts to secure

critical raw materials, the EU should refocus resources from general support toward financial incentives for European private sector entry into CRM supply chains. Furthermore, strategic public-private partnerships (PPPs) must be deployed to provide de-risking guarantees, long-term offtake agreements, and subsidized financing to EU companies willing to invest in CRM mining and refining.

Third, in a globalized world, considering China's non-negligible geoeconomic power and leverage over the supply chain, the EU cannot sever ties and economic relations with China overnight. This means that conditioned engagement is essential when dealing with China via investment or joint ventures. The EU must be careful not to inadvertently transfer crucial assets or become a trojan horse for Chinese influence on the continent. Thus, the EU should rely on instruments such as investment screenings through the FDI Screening Regulation (2019) (EIES, 2025). This regulation ensures that scrutiny and screening are conducted for strategic investment sectors. This initiative allows the EU to strengthen and synchronize its cooperation across Member States to amplify defensive mechanisms and prevent China from exploiting the weakest link (EIES, 2025).

Finally, around all the discussion of competitiveness and growth, a sinister agenda is trying to creep in: the proposed simplification omnibus by the European Commission seeks to slash sustainability regulations and allow for "deregulation that rewards laggards" (Mendiluce & Hooper, 2025, para. 7). These proposals claim to scale back sustainability regulations, under the guise of reducing red tape, which could undermine long-term industrial competitiveness and climate objectives. Mendiluce & Hooper (2025) argue that the clear and consistent implementation of the Green Deal and its regulations provides a stable context for sustainable investment and serves as the EU's de facto growth strategy, necessitating strong ambition, regulatory clarity, and significant investment to maintain global competitiveness.

While simplifying regulations to support small and medium enterprises and avoiding overlaps and contradictory demands to accelerate the transition to clean energy is beneficial, a wholesale rollback of sustainability reporting and due diligence requirements would be detrimental (Gros, 2025; Mendiluce & Hooper, 2025). Such measures are essential for companies to manage risks, attract investment, and capitalize on market opportunities, especially in a global context where China continues to expand its influence in the low-carbon market.

Conclusion

This article has utilized a new geoeconomic framework by Blackwill & Harris (2016) to assess how China's dominance in the EV and battery value chain translates into significant geopolitical leverage. This study demonstrated China's centrality in global value chains, market monopolies over key battery materials, and monopsony power as the world's largest buyer and processor of critical minerals. This dominance over global battery, EV production and innovation, while promising for the green transition, not only cements China's economic leadership but also grants it significant geopolitical leverage. By controlling key materials, refining capacity, and advanced battery technology, China can dictate market conditions, influence trade policies, and potentially use supply restrictions as a strategic tool in international negotiation. Thus, as global efforts aim to transition to clean energy, other economies will increasingly rely on Chinese supply chains.

Over the last five years, the European Union has shifted its approach to the EV and battery market in light of China's rise and dominance. What once was a market-driven relationship, where European car brands were selling in China and Chinese batteries were powering the European shift towards electric vehicles and the green transition, this sector has become a strategic concern to the EU.

Bolstered by Russia's aggression of Ukraine which exposed critical dependencies, the EU is on a mission to bolster its resilience and plug into alternative networks and markets to reduce single-point failures, meaning not relying on one country alone for certain needs and services (Tenev, 2024). Consequently, the EU has coalesced around von der Leyen's infamous "de-risking" agenda, which aims to reduce critical dependencies on China through domestic capacity-building and targeted defensive trade measures (Arendse, 2023).

Despite the EU implementing defensive measures like strategic alliances and tariffs, these are insufficient to solve the structural weaknesses in the European green technology industry. Internal conflicts, legislative restrictions, and an excessive reliance on imported resources further hinder the EU's efforts, making it vulnerable to both strategic dependence and economic pressure. The EU must increase domestic capacity, encourage private sector participation in CRM supply chains, improve investment screening, and uphold legislative ambition under the Green Deal to restore leverage and guarantee strategic autonomy and remain competitive in the global low-carbon race.

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